

Serum Cystatin C Level as a Potential Indicator of Hepatic Fibrosis in Patients with Chronic Hepatitis B

Kronik Hepatit B'li Hastalarda Hepatik Fibrozisin Potansiyel Bir Göstergesi Olarak Serum Sistatin C Düzeyi

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The aim of this study is to investigate the usability of serum cystatin C levels as a non-invasive fibrosis marker in patients with chronic hepatitis B.

Material and Method: The study included 122 patients [63 chronic active hepatitis B (HBeAg+chronic hepatitis B), 29 chronic inactive hepatitis B (HBeAg-chronic HBV infection), and 30 patients on oral antiviral therapy (at least 6 months of treatment and HBVDNA negative)] and 30 healthy controls. According to the Modified Ishak Score, chronic active hepatitis B patients with a fibrosis score of 0–1 were classified as having “no fibrosis/mild fibrosis” and 2–6 as having “advanced (severe) fibrosis”. Statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between the groups.

Results: A significant difference was found in terms of HBVDNA ($p=0.007$), and the histological activity index ($p<0.001$) between the no fibrosis/mild fibrosis and advanced fibrosis groups. HBVDNA ($p<0.001$), cystatin C level ($p<0.001$) were found to be significantly different between advanced fibrosis and oral antiviral treatment patient groups. HBVDNA ($p=0.000$), and cystatin C ($p<0.001$) levels were found to be significantly different among patients with chronic active hepatitis and receiving oral antiviral therapy. The difference between chronic active hepatitis and healthy control groups was significant in terms of cystatin C ($p=0.010$) levels.

Conclusion: The serum cystatin C level changes in parallel with the HBVDNA level suggests that it is a marker that can be used as an indicator of replication and therefore indirectly of hepatic fibrosis.

Keywords: Cystatin C, hepatic fibrosis, chronic hepatitis B

ÖZ

Amaç: Bu çalışmanın amacı, kronik hepatit B'li hastalarda serum sistatin C düzeylerinin non-invaziv bir fibrozis belirteci olarak kullanılabilirliğini araştırmaktır.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Çalışmaya 122 hasta [63 kronik aktif hepatit B (HBeAg+ kronik hepatit B), 29 kronik inaktif hepatit B (HBeAg- kronik HBV enfeksiyonu) ve 30 oral antiviral tedavi alan (en az 6 aydır tedavi gören ve HBV DNA negatif) hasta] ile 30 sağlıklı kontrol dahil edildi. Modifiye Ishak Sko- runa göre, kronik aktif hepatit B hastalarında fibrozis skoru 0–1 olanlar “fibrozis yok/hafif fibrozis”, 2–6 olanlar ise “ileri (şiddetli) fibrozis” olarak sınıflandırıldı. Gruplar arasındaki ilişkiyi belirlemek için istatistiksel analiz yapıldı.

Bulgular: Fibrozis yok/hafif fibrozis ve ileri fibrozis grupları arasında HBV DNA ($p=0,007$) ve histolojik aktivite indeksi ($p<0,001$) açısından anlamlı fark bulundu. İleri fibrozis ve oral antiviral tedavi alan hasta grupları arasında HBV DNA ($p<0,001$) ve sistatin C düzeyi ($p<0,001$) anlamlı olarak farklıydı. Kronik aktif hepatit ve oral antiviral tedavi alan hastalar arasında HBV DNA ($p=0,000$) ve sistatin C ($p<0,001$) düzeyleri anlamlı farklılık gösterdi. Kronik aktif hepatit ile sağlıklı kontrol grupları arasındaki sistatin C düzeyleri farkı da anlamlıydı ($p=0,010$).

Sonuç: Serum sistatin C düzeyinin HBV DNA düzeyi ile paralel değişim göstermesi, bunun replikasyonun ve dolaylı olarak hepatic fibrozisin bir göstergesi olarak kullanılabilirliğini düşündürmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sistatin C, hepatic fibrozis, kronik hepatit B

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic hepatitis B is the most common cause of chronic liver disease and may progress to cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), and liver failure (1). Although host-related and viral factors are effective in disease progression, the most important factor is HBV DNA levels. In the management of chronic liver disease and chronic hepatitis B, the presence and severity of hepatic fibrosis are important factors in making treatment decisions and following up (2). Determining the appropriate treatment strategy for the patient is based on the serum ALT level, the serum HBV DNA levels, and liver histology. For patients with serum HBV DNA levels >2000 IU/mL and elevated serum ALT levels, treatment should be decided based on liver biopsy and/or non-invasive methods (3). Liver biopsy is the gold standard for evaluating fibrosis. Various non-invasive markers and imaging methods are used and being developed to evaluate fibrosis instead of an invasive procedure such as a liver biopsy that may have complications. Transforming growth factor β (TGF β) is the most important cytokine in liver fibrogenesis. TGF β is a potent stimulator of cystatin C secretion in vascular smooth muscle cells (4). It triggers the differentiation of stellate cells (hepatic stellate cells, HSC) into hepatic myofibroblasts. Cystatin C expression increases during myofibroblast differentiation under TGF β stimulation (5). In chronic hepatitis C, fibrosis stage appears to be correlated with plasma TGF β levels (6). These findings led to the opinion that cystatin C levels may also be associated with fibrosis in chronic hepatitis B. The aim of this study is to investigate the usability of serum cystatin C levels as a non-invasive fibrosis marker in patients with chronic hepatitis B.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was conducted with the approval of the Ethics Committee of Ankara Dışkapı Yıldırım Beyazıt Training and Research Hospital (Date: November 3, 2014; Approval No: 17/18), and all procedures were performed in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

This study included 122 patients [63 patients with chronic active hepatitis B (HBeAg+ chronic hepatitis B), 29 patients with chronic inactive hepatitis B (HBeAg-chronic HBV infection), and 30 patients on oral antiviral therapy (at least 6 months of treatment and HBV DNA negative)] who applied to the Ankara Dışkapı Yıldırım Beyazıt Training and Research Hospital Gastroenterology Clinic between November 15, 2014, and May 30, 2015, as well as 30 healthy control groups. All patients who underwent liver biopsy were categorized as having "chronic active hepatitis B (HBeAg+chronic hepatitis B)". Patients with HBV DNA ≤ 2000 IU/ml, ALT normal, and HBeAg (-) who did not undergo biopsy and did not receive treatment were classified as "chronic inactive hepatitis B (HBeAg-chronic HBV Infection)". Patients

who were in the 6th month of their treatment and became negative for HBV DNA were classified as "under oral antiviral therapy". Healthy individuals without any disease were classified as "healthy controls".

According to the Modified Ishak Score (7), patients with a fibrosis score of 0–1 were classified as having "no fibrosis/mild fibrosis" (39 patients) and patients with a fibrosis score of 2–6 as having "advanced (severe) fibrosis" (24 patients). Patients were evaluated with fibrosis scores obtained from liver biopsy and age, gender, HBV DNA levels, serum cystatin C levels.

Plasma cystatin C was analyzed using the BIOENDER Human Cystatin C Elisa Kit on a Roche cobas c702 analyzer.

Liver biopsy samples were sent to the pathology laboratory in formol. Samples with formalin were stained with "hematoxylin-eosin" stain for activity and "Masson's trichrome" stain for fibrosis. In liver biopsies, histopathologically, the degree of inflammation and necrosis was determined by the Modified Ishak Activity and Fibrosis Score.

Statistical Analysis

For data analysis, the SPSS v22.0 (IBM Corp, Armonk, NY, USA) statistical program was used. Descriptive statistics were presented as mean \pm standard deviation or mean (maximum-minimum) for continuous variables, and as number of cases and % for categorical variables. Non-parametric tests were used because the distribution of the data was not normal. Mann-Whitney U, Chi square and T tests were used for the comparison of groups. $p<0.05$ was considered statistically significant, and the results were interpreted accordingly.

RESULTS

122 patients and 30 healthy controls were included in the study. 55 of the patients (45.1%) were female and, 67 (54.9%) were male. There were 63 patients (41.4%) with chronic active hepatitis B [39 patients with no fibrosis or mild fibrosis (25.7%), and 24 patients with advanced fibrosis (15.8%)]. There were 29 patients (19.1%) with chronic inactive hepatitis B, 30 patients (19.7%) on oral antiviral therapy, and 30 healthy controls (19.7%). The general characteristics, laboratory values and pathology data are given in **Table 1**.

As shown in **Table 2**, a significant difference was found in terms of HBV DNA ($p=0.007$), and the histological activity index ($p<0.001$).

There was no gender difference between the advanced fibrosis and oral antiviral treatment patient groups ($p=0.975$). Age ($p=0.004$), HBV DNA ($p<0.001$), cystatin C level ($p<0.001$) were found to be significantly different between advanced fibrosis and oral antiviral treatment patient groups. These findings are given in **Table 3**.

Table 1. General Features of Patients

	Chronic Active Hepatitis B	Chronic Inactive Hepatitis B	Oral Antiviral Treatment
Number of Patients (n)	63	29	30
Age (sd)	43 (±10)	46 (±15)	50 (±12)
Gender (female/male)	29/34	16/13	10/20
HBV DNA (IU/ml)	11.911.442 (2200-210.000.000)	291 (0-1760)	0
Cystatin C (ng/ml)	2188 (726-8424)	1680 (695-4456)	1225 (581-5476)
ALT (U/L) mean (min-max)	71 (11-623)	28 (13-80)	22 (8-51)
AST (U/L) mean (min-max)	51 (16-356)	25 (15-52)	25 (15-63)
Albumin (g/dL) mean (min-max)	4,4 (3,8-5)	4,5 (4-5)	4,5 (4-5,1)
Creatinine (mg/dL) mean (min-max)	0,8 (0,5-1,2)	0,9 (0,4-1,15)	0,9 (0,6-1,2)
Platelet(thousand/mm ³) mean (min-max)	219 (67-382)	239 (148-335)	246 (136-343)
AAR mean (min-max)	0,922 (0,31-2,9)	1,002 (0,597-1,538)	1,211 (0,641-2,172)
APRI mean (min-max)	0,281 (0,051-1,736)	0,109 (0,045-0,25)	0,110 (0,047-0,354)
Histological activity index (mean) (min-max)	5 (1-13)	-	-
Fibrosis stage (n, %)			
0	12 (%19)	-	-
1	27 (%43)	-	-
2	14 (%22)	-	-
3	4 (%6)	-	-
4	3 (%5)	-	-
5	3 (%5)	-	-
6	-	-	-

HBV DNA: Hepatitis B virus deoxyribonucleic acid, AST: Aspartate Aminotransferase, ALT: Alanine Aminotransferase, AAR: AST/ALT Ratio, APRI: AST to Platelet Ratio Index

Table 2. Comparison of no fibrosis/mild fibrosis and severe fibrosis group

	No Fibrosis/Mild Fibrosis (<2)	Severe Fibrosis (≥2)	p-value
Number of Patients (n)	39	24	-
Age (sd)	44 (± 11,4)	42,2 (± 8,3)	0,581
Gender (female/male)	20/19	9/15	0,42
HBV DNA (IU/ml) mean (min-max)	2.242.046 (2247-41.000.000)	27.624.210 (2200-21.0000.000)	< 0,05
Cystatin C (ng/ml) mean (min-max)	2085 (742-8424)	2354 (726-6969)	0,445
Histological Activity Index mean (min-max)	4 (1 - 9)	7 (3 - 13)	<0,001

HBV DNA: Hepatitis B virus deoxyribonucleic acid

Table 3. Comparison of severe fibrosis and oral antiviral treatment group

	Severe Fibrosis (≥2)	Oral Antiviral Treatment	p-value
Number of Patients (n)	24	30	-
Age (sd)	42,2 (± 8,3)	50(±12)	< 0,05
Gender (female/male)	9/15	10/20	0,975
HBV DNA (IU/ml) mean (min-max)	27.624.210 (2200-210.000.000)	0	<0,001
Cystatin C (ng/ml) mean (min-max)	2354 (726-6969)	1225 (581-5476)	<0,001

HBV DNA: Hepatitis B virus deoxyribonucleic acid

There were no significant differences in gender, age and cystatin C between the groups. HBV DNA ($p<0.001$) was different between groups. These findings are given in **Table 4**.

Age ($p=0.002$), HBV DNA ($p=0.000$), and cystatin C ($p<0.001$) levels were found to be significantly different among patients with chronic active hepatitis and receiving oral antiviral therapy. These findings are given in **Table 4**.

The difference between chronic active hepatitis and healthy control groups was significant in terms of

cystatin C ($p=0.010$) levels. There was a statistically insignificant difference in cystatin C ($p=0.303$) levels between chronic inactive hepatitis and healthy control. These findings are given in **Table 5**.

The comparison of cystatin C in different groups is summarized in **charts 1 and 2**. **Chart 1** summarizes the comparison of cystatin C levels among the study groups, clearly demonstrating higher levels in active HBV patients. **Chart 2** illustrates the relationship between fibrosis stage and cystatin C levels, supporting the findings presented in **Tables 3-4**.

Table 4. Comparison of Chronic Active Hepatitis B with Chronic Inactive Hepatitis B Group and Oral Antiviral Treatment Group

	Chronic Active Hepatitis B	Chronic Inactive Hepatitis B	p-value	Chronic Active Hepatitis B	Oral Antiviral Treatment	p-value
Number of Patients (n)	63	29	-	63	30	
Age (sd)	43(±10)	46(±15)	0,138	43(±10)	50(±12)	< 0.05
Gender (female/ male)	29/34	16/13	0,249	29/34	10/20	
HBV DNA (IU/ml) mean (min–max)	11.911.442 (2200–210.000.000)	291 (0–1760)	<0,001	11.911.442 (2200–210.000.000)	0	<0,001
Cystatin C (ng/ml) mean (min–max)	2188 (726–8424)	1680 (695–4456)	0,167	2188 (726–8424)	1225 (581–5476)	<0,001

HBV DNA: Hepatitis B virus deoxyribonucleic acid

Table 5. Comparison of Chronic Active Hepatitis B and Chronic Inactive Hepatitis B Group

	Chronic Active Hepatitis B	Healthy Control	p-value	Chronic Inactive Hepatitis B	Healthy Control	p-value
Number of Patients (n)	63	30		29	30	
Cystatin C (ng/ml) mean (min–max)	2188 (726-8424)	1387 (728-2609)	<0.05	1680 (695-4456)	1387 (728-2609)	0.303

Chart 2. Comparison of Cystatin C in different groups

Regarding cystatin C, no statistically significant difference was observed between the no/mild-fibrosis and advanced-fibrosis groups ($p=0.445$), whereas levels were lower in patients receiving oral-antiviral therapy than in those with advanced fibrosis ($p<0.001$), and higher in chronic active HBV than in the treatment group ($p<0.001$); cystatin C was also higher in chronic active HBV than in healthy controls ($p=0.010$) but not different between inactive HBV and controls ($p=0.303$). Taken together, these patterns suggest that serum cystatin C may mirror viral replication and necroinflammatory activity rather than fixed fibrosis stage, which is consistent with reports showing higher cystatin C in chronic liver disease and its relationship to necroinflammation/fibrogenic activity (10–12).

There were some limitations in our study. Since we could not evaluate active patients at the time of diagnosis and reevaluate them at the end of the 6th month of their treatment, we could not show regression of cystatin C and fibrosis with treatment. However, we know that in the 6th month of their treatment, with the demonstration of HBV replication, which regressed with treatment, serum cystatin C level, as an indirect indicator, may also play a role in showing regressed fibrosis (8). In addition, the limited number of patients and the single-center design of the study should also be considered as limitations.

DISCUSSION

Previous studies have reported a close association between viral replication and fibrosis progression in chronic HBV [8,9]. In line with these data, HBV DNA levels were higher in the advanced-fibrosis group than in the no/mild-fibrosis group ($p=0.007$) and differed significantly between advanced fibrosis vs. oral-antiviral treatment and chronic active vs. chronic inactive groups (both $p<0.001$), supporting the link between replication and disease severity.

CONCLUSION

Serum cystatin C levels appear to vary in parallel with HBV DNA levels, suggesting that cystatin C may serve as an indirect marker of viral replication. However, our results did not demonstrate a significant correlation between cystatin C and histological fibrosis stage. Therefore, while cystatin C could be considered a potential indicator in the context of HBV replication, further large-scale and longitudinal studies are needed before it can be accepted as a reliable non-invasive marker of hepatic fibrosis.

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: The study was conducted with the approval of the Ankara Dışkapı Yıldırım Beyazıt Training and Research Hospital Ethics Committee (Date: November 3, 2014; Approval No: 17/18)

Informed Consent: All patients signed the free and informed consent form.

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